

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PROMOTION OF WORK IN FOOD INDUSTRY INSTITUTIONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7391042>

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Abstract

The rational organization of management is the basis of the efficient operation of food industry enterprises in Azerbaijan, and the source of management is human resources and the optimal direction of these resources in appropriate directions. Therefore, ensuring its effective use is a strategically important aspect in the activity of any enterprise. If we consider this important aspect from the point of view of continuous strengthening and improvement, it should be noted that the main role belongs to the management of human resources and directly to one of its most important functions, that is, motivation. As we know, with the development of social relations in modern society, the requirements and needs imposed by enterprises on employees also change. In addition to the material factor used in the activity of enterprises in the economy of Azerbaijan, it is important to add moral encouragement and social benefits in an intensive form. Innovation-based development of production and provision of services regularly affects and improves the primarily material forms of employee stimulation. The share of payments based on the results of the enterprise's economic activity in the financial payment is increasing, more importance is attached to the development of corporate thinking among employees, and the system of social benefits is developing.

Keywords: food industry, management, labor motivation, economic stimulation.

The intensification of economic processes leads to various changes in the industry as well as in various fields, making decisions of various nature and applying modern methods in management. The food industry, which is considered one of the important and socially oriented priority areas of the industry, stands out for its specificity and strategic importance for the country. Recently, the increase in the number of food industry enterprises representing the domestic market in Azerbaijan has also affected the quality factor. Thus, providing goods and services to various consumer segments intensifies the process of competition between food industry enterprises. In such a case, enterprises equipped with modern production equipment can gain a leading position only as a result of the professionalism of the staff. In this regard, stimulation of human resources in food industry enterprises is of great importance.

Motivation is a psychophysiological process that controls human behavior and forms internal motivational factors acting through self-awareness. "Motivation" and "stimulation" are two closely related concepts. However, if the concept of "stimulus" is mainly used for material or moral motivation, "motive" is used more broadly and covers all aspects of employee behavior. It is usually divided into external, internal and

there are various motivational factors. Internal motivation factors can be:

- self-actualization;
- self-affirmation;
- creativity;
- certainty;
- interest;
- the need for communication.

Refers to external factors of motivation:

- financial resources;
- career;
- position in society and recognition, etc.
- can be positive or negative nature motives.

Personnel motivation is carried out at three interrelated levels, each of which has its own characteristics. Each employee has long-term, medium-term and short-term motivation at a personal level. The main principles of motivation at the personal level are that the management communicates with the employee's interests in a timely, individual approach. One of the important factors of effective motivation of the employee at the personal level is the clarity of the issue, its compatibility with the employee's competences and interests. At the group level, there is motivation for productive and effective group work.

The motivation of group work leads to defining the range of tasks that can be performed in the group and creating optimal conditions for group interaction. The main factors of effective group motivation are group characteristics, leadership and management style and principles. Labor motivation of personnel at the organizational level is carried out through economic and political stimulation methods supported by all management subsystems. One of the important factors of effective motivation at the organizational level is the image of the organization and the reputation of top managers, as well as its adequacy to strategic goals. The principles of organizational motivation are the balance of responsibility, management and interests of all categories of employees. Thus, the systematic approach to personnel motivation is based on a comprehensive consideration of the psychological principles of the motivational process of individual and group activity, as well as the methods of effective recruitment motivation, retention and efficient operation.

In the modern management process, more attention is paid to the corporate culture of the enterprise as one of the most important motivational incentives for personnel. Organizational culture is a set of ideas and values that are shared by all members of an organization and set guidelines for people's behavior and actions. Several factors influence its formation. As a rule, the main factor that determines the style of relations between employees is the character and views of the head of the enterprise. In the organizational culture, the management of the enterprise is more interested in the mechanism of influence on the behavior and work of the enterprise employees. Management studies show that companies with a strong organizational culture achieve effective results in the use of human resources. The most important task of the manager is to manage the motivational process in such a way that his behavior helps to achieve the goals of the organization. People working in modern organizations are generally better educated and wealthier than in the past, so the motivations for their work are more complex and difficult to influence. There is no single rule for developing a mechanism to motivate employees to work efficiently. The effectiveness of motivation, like other problems in management, is always related to the specific situation. The listed organizational and moral-psychological methods provide different motivation depending on the tenure, but after a certain period, none of them provide adequate motivation, so job satisfaction decreases.

The level of wages, including bonuses and social benefits, is the most important factor affecting the productivity and loyalty of employees. In personnel management, motivation is the process of activating the motives of employees and creating incentives to motivate them to work effectively. The personnel motivation system can be based on different methods. Their choice depends on the development of the incentive system in the enterprise, the general management system and the characteristics of the enterprise itself. Sociological studies show that wages and personal benefits have the greatest weight among the forms of motivation, followed by various types of

bonuses, health insurance, access to credit and financial assistance.

The following forms of motivation are also important:

- good moral environment in the team;
- good working conditions for career growth;
- payment of vouchers;
- social holidays.

Since enterprises employ employees of different ages and qualifications at different stages of their careers, the incentive system should include various means of influence. Thus, the designer is more interested in the high quality of the product or technology he develops, and the top manager is more interested in the organization's reputation, market position and participation in the company's profits, etc. It should be noted that the main needs of young professionals in the formative stage of their careers are self-affirmation, achieving independence and a salary level that ensures normal living conditions. Over time, the priority of needs changes in different directions: health, high wages and opportunities for self-expression, security and stability. It is clear that the use of single corporate incentives will not ensure high management efficiency.

The next important element of stimulation measures is related to career and professional advancement. The main direction here is the implementation of purposeful work for career planning. Career planning can begin with a joint discussion and agreement between the manager and the employee about career expectations. It is important for the manager to understand who the employee sees himself as after a certain period of time, which areas are promising for him. At the appropriate stage, it is appropriate to discuss the employee's readiness for training and his participation in various projects and related fields, which is important from the point of view of his development. This approach demonstrates the company's interest in the employee, its focus on growth issues that concern the employee. However, the risks associated with overestimated employee expectations and unmanaged promises must be minimized.

The food industry is a branch of light industry, the totality of the production of food products in the form of finished or semi-finished products. In the system of the agro-industrial complex of Azerbaijan, the food industry is closely connected with agriculture and trade as a supplier of raw materials. Some areas of the food industry are moving towards resource regions, and the other part is moving towards consumption regions. . The economic opportunities of the food industry, which is important in providing the country with food, mainly depend on the dynamic increase in the production of crops and livestock-related goods.

If food safety is not ensured as a factor protecting the statehood and sovereignty of Azerbaijan, which is the most important component of social and demographic policy, then improving the quality of life of the population by guaranteeing high living standards, a strategic national priority, cannot be realized. Solving such complex problems is possible only on the basis of sustainable, coordinated and unified development of all

links of the agricultural system, which is agriculture and processing industry. This is primarily due to the fact that agricultural production itself is dual. Thus, a certain part of the products produced in agriculture goes to the direct consumption of the population. However, the other part of agricultural products only serves as raw material for processing. In turn, the processing industry affects the development of agriculture. Because it forms the demand for agricultural products, their structure, standardization and quality requirements, it stimulates the specialization of agricultural organizations and the formation of raw material zones around processing enterprises. Enterprises of the food and processing industry significantly affect the employment and stability of incomes of the rural population, the development of the industrial and social infrastructure of rural areas, and the general production culture of rural settlements.

The reorganization of a number of production enterprises and the continuation of the successfully implemented agrarian reforms in Azerbaijan have increased the volume of various locally produced food products and reduced the intensity of their import to our country. Products produced at the expense of domestic resources have created alternative options for the country's consumers.

The change of the socio-economic development paradigm of the country implies a transition to a sustainable development model in which the sectors of the agro-food complex are given an important place. Numerous studies confirm that there is a direct relationship between the level of development of the processing industry, the system of relations between agriculture and other sectors, and other sectors of the agro-food complex, and the degree of closeness between economic subjects. Many researchers note that although the processing industry is characterized by great integration activity, the central link of the food complex is agriculture. This depends on a number of conditions. The first is the original base industry for the production of agricultural products, raw materials and food. Second, the structure, volume, and distribution of commodity agricultural products predetermine the directions, scale, and, in some cases, the location of processing plants in the processing industry. Third, agriculture is a renewable resource base that, with proper treatment, increases production potential. Fourth, the social efficiency of agricultural production ultimately serves as a criterion for the feasibility of industrial processing of agricultural raw materials and the construction of new processing facilities.

The insufficient level of development of innovations and the low activity of business do not help the application of modern achievements of scientific and technical progress to production. The level of competitiveness of the modern innovative economy is mainly determined by the quality of professional personnel. The answer to this challenge for Azerbaijan consists in eliminating the current negative trends in human development characterized by population growth and increased competition with European and Asian markets for qualified personnel. A shortage of

highly qualified engineers and workers can slow down economic growth in the food and processing industries.

Modernization, which is the main factor in the elimination of accumulated problems in the economy and social sphere, and the protection of the sovereignty and integrity of the state, requires great efforts with the involvement of large-scale financial, material and human resources in a short historical period.

The food industry is an example of what the Azerbaijani economy is capable of in a favorable investment environment. The payback period of investments in industrial enterprises is much shorter than that of investments in primary industries. The return on investments can be felt after one or two years. Such conditions are quite acceptable for most investors. The capacity of the Azerbaijani food market is currently estimated at billions of dollars. There is reason to believe that the market will continue to grow in the future. After all, the real income of the population has been increasing for the fourth year already, and it is this factor that determines the dynamics of the food market. In addition, the quality of local food products has been increasing in recent years, and most Azerbaijani products are superior in quality to imported ones. For this reason, and in connection with the cases of import and sale of low-quality and counterfeit goods, the demand for imported food is decreasing. Enterprises have appropriate technological resources in order to obtain information related to the sector to which they belong. Despite this, it is not possible to carry out a number of trainings related to the development of the professional characteristics of employees in enterprises. In order for enterprises to stand out from others, as well as to be ahead in terms of human resources, they should be given different trainings, including increasing the loyalty of employees to the enterprise.

State regulation of the quality of food products is carried out through standardization and certification. In order to develop the initiative of commodity producers, the state gave them the right to develop and approve the technical characteristics of products, which allows to expand the range of food products and diversify their design. At the same time, the current situation in the local food industry, which is characterized by the continuation of deep crisis events, implies the application of various economic mechanisms and measures to effectively get out of the crisis. One of the ways to restore Azerbaijan's food potential is to use the opportunities of enterprises to integrate into corporations connected with technological connections and the food market. At the same time, the privatization of food processing enterprises contributed to the further isolation of local participants in the food market. Given the large-scale decline in production, the country faced the challenge of maintaining economic food security for the first time in post-war decades. The areas of the food industry are classified in different directions depending on the characteristic features that form the basis of the formation of the industry - the purpose of the products, the nature of the raw materials used, the technology used, etc. The food industry includes mining, processing and processing industries.

Extractive industries include salt, fishing and part of the non-alcoholic industry - the extraction and bottling of mineral waters. The rest of the food industry is the processing of food raw materials and the division of food production into processing and food industry. These are nothing but different stages of raw material processing and finished product production. Depending on the characteristics of production organization, seasonal and non-seasonal production areas are distinguished. As a rule, seasonal industries include most processing industries, i.e. primary processing of seasonal agricultural raw materials and partially fishing industry. According to the method of processing raw materials and semi-finished products, the food industry is divided into sectors dominated by biochemical, microbiological and chemical bases, and industrial sectors dominated by mechanical basis for processing labor objects.

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FISHING: REAL SECTOR OF ECONOMY OF NORTHERN REGIONS OF RUSSIA (PROBLEMS&PROSPECTS)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7391064>

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РЫБОЛОВСТВО: РЕАЛЬНЫЙ СЕКТОР ЭКОНОМИКИ СЕВЕРНЫХ РЕГИОНОВ РОССИИ (ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ)

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Abstract

In water areas of RK, on data of State Report (*About Condition of Surrounding Ambiences of the Republic of Komi in 2018*), near 50 types of fish had been numbered. This forms 0.23% of world variety and 14.3% of the country (water areas of RF) variety of fishes (*Ponomarev, Zaharov, 2022*). The main region of industrial fishing is Pechorskij water basin (96.1% of general catch). The remainder of the catch was accounted for water basins of Vychehda, Mezen, Kara, Cobra and Letka. The fishing is realized for research and control purposes. Use of fishing areas is approbated for organization of amateur and sporting fishing. Also it leads fishing to development of aquaculture (fish herding), saving of fishes. General catch was in limits of 1 thous. t.

Аннотация

В водоемах РК по данным Госдоклада («О состоянии окружающей среды Республики Коми в 2018 году») насчитывалось около 50 видов рыб. Это составляет 0,23% мирового и 14,3% странового (водоемы РФ) разнообразия рыб (*Пономарев, Захаров, 2022*). Основным районом промышленного рыболовства является Печорский бассейн (96,1% общих уловов). Остаток улова приходится на бассейны Вычегды, Мезени, Кары, Кобры и Летки. Осуществляется рыболовство в научно-исследовательских и контрольных целях. Апробируется использование рыбопромысловых участков для организации любительского и спортивного рыболовства. Ведется также рыболовство для развития аквакультуры (рыбоводство), сохранения рыб. Общий вылов был в пределах 1 тыс. т.

Keywords: fish, region, ambience, economy, catch

Ключевые слова: рыба, регион, среда, экономика, улов

Введение. Начиная с 1917 г., в Российской Федерации был сформирован и сегодня успешно

функционирует рыбопромышленный комплекс северных регионов. В ходе проводимых научных исследований в северных регионах рассматривается